

D9.1. Communication and dissemination plan

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-LC-BAT-10-2020 GA No. 963540
Project title	Manufacturing and assembly of modular and reusable EV battery for environment-friendly and lightweight mobility
Duration of the project	2021 – 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP9
Document due Date:	31/03/2020
Actual date of delivery	31/03/2020
Leader of this deliverable	EUT
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	19/03/2021	Marina Presas , Miriam Vendrell (EUT) / Christian Hannemann (FW-IWU)	Draft version sent to partners
0.2	22/03/2021	Alberto Gómez / Eduard Piqueras (EUT)	Revision
0.3	29/03/2021	Marina Presas (EUT) / Christian Hanneman (FW-IWU)	Production of final version
1.0	31/03/2021	Eduard Piqueras (EUT)	Final revision and submission

Executive summary

The present confidential document details the MARBEL project communication and dissemination plan, aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. FRAUNHOFER IWU and EUT are responsible for designing and implementing MARBEL communication and dissemination strategy, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

The channels and platforms considered in the communication and dissemination plan are: social media channels, official website, materials to be distributed in key events, media relations to specialized media outlets, scientific publications, the organization of workshops and training activities, and attendance to strategic conferences, fairs and congresses where the project can be presented, training activities and the organisation of industry workshops and direct dissemination activities, among others.

This deliverable details the target groups, key messages addressed to each main group of stakeholders, communication and dissemination activities planned, requirements and the process of reporting and monitoring communication activities.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet	2
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	5
List of abbreviations	6
Introduction	7
1. Communication and dissemination plan	8
1.1 Target of communication and dissemination	8
1.2 Channels	9
1.3 Key messages	9
2. Communication and dissemination management	12
2.1 Distribution of responsibilities	12
2.2 Requirements	12
2.3 Monitoring and reporting	13
2.3.1 Activities reporting	13
2.3.2 Communication and dissemination activities KPIs	13
2.3.3 KPIs reporting	14
2.3.4 Risks and mitigation measures	17
3. Communication and dissemination tools and activities	18
3.1 Project branding and templates	18
3.1.1 MARBEL logo	18
3.1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual	19
3.1.3 Templates	23
3.2 Website	27
3.2.1 Website structure	28
3.2.2 Website content	29
3.2.3 Layout	49
3.2.4 Managing and updating policy	50
3.2.5 Analytics	50
3.2.6 Site hosting, installation and maintenance	50
3.2.7 Data protection	51
3.3 Digital / printed materials	51
3.4 Audiovisual materials	52
3.5 Social Media	53
3.5.1 Twitter	53
3.5.2 YouTube	55

3.5.3 Partners channels	55
3.6 Media relations	57
3.6.1 Press release propose calendar	58
3.7 Academic dissemination	58
3.7.1 Scientific publications	58
3.7.2 Participation to events targeting the academic community	59
3.7.3 Webinars	60
3.7.4 Training activities.....	60
3.8 Dissemination to the industry	61
3.8.1 Participation to Exhibitions and conferences	61
3.8.2 Industrial events	61
3.8.3 One-to-one meetings.....	62
3.9 Dissemination to the society	63
3.10 Clustering activities	63
3.10.1 Joint actions with sister projects.....	63
3.10.2 Joint actions with EV user associations	65
3.10.3 Joint actions with EU clusters, associations and initiatives	65
3.11 Activities calendar	69
4. Annex	71
4.0 Website privacy policy	71
4.1 Website legal warning	73
4.2 Website cookies policy.....	75

List of figures

Figure 1: Stakeholder groups.....	8
Figure 2: MARBEL Communication and Dissemination channels	9
Figure 3: Risk management process	17
Figure 4: Risk management matrix	17
Figure 4: Full Colour logo and logo version with colour background	19
.....	19
Figure 5: Black and white logo version negative/positive.....	19
Figure 6: MARBEL project colours.....	20
Figure 7: Use of fonts for promotional materials	20
Figure 8: Use of fonts for internal documents and deliverables	21
Figure 9: View of stationery materials	21
Figure 10: MARBEL graphic resources.....	22
Figure 11: Two versions of Twitter header templates	23
Figure 12: View of MARBEL presentation template.....	24
Figure 13: View of some deliverable template pages	25
Figure 14: MARBEL agenda template	26
Figure 15: Snapchat of MARBEL minutes' template.....	27
Figure 16: MARBEL letter template	27

Figure 17: Website structure	28
Figure 19: View of MARBEL homepage designed - https://marbel-project.eu	33
Figure 20: View of "About the project" page - https://marbel-project.eu/about-marbel/	37
Figure 21: View of partners page - https://marbel-project.eu/partners/	38
Figure 22: Example of individual partners' pages	39
Figure 23: View of "News & Events" page	45
Figure 24: View of MARBEL results page - https://marbel-project.eu/results/	46
Figure 25: View of contact page - https://marbel-project.eu/contact/	48
Figure 18: MARBEL website layout	49
Figure 27: MARBEL website footer	49
Figure 27: View of MARBEL header	49
Figure 29: View of Matomo Analytics panel	50
Figure 30: View of cookies banner allowing the user to deactivate non-necessary cookies	51
Figure 19: Proposed design of MARBEL flyer (left) and rollups (right)	52
Figure 20: View of MARBEL twitter account	53
Figure 21: View of Twitter analytics profile	55

List of tables

Table 1: Table to record the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners	13
Table 2: MARBEL Communication and Dissemination KPIs	13
Table 3: Website and social media analytics reporting table	14
Table 4: Table to report scientific publications	15
Table 5: Media Clipping table	16
Table 6: Risks and mitigation measures	17
Table 7: Partners Social Media channels	55
Table 8: List of specialized outlets	57
Table 9: Preliminary press release calendar	58
Table 10: List of identified journals	59
Table 11: Identified events targeting academia	59
Table 12: List of industrial exhibitions and conferences	61
Table 13: MARBEL sister projects	64

List of abbreviations

<i>AEDP</i>	<i>Spanish Data Protection Agency</i>
<i>BMS</i>	<i>Battery Management System</i>
<i>BP</i>	<i>Battery Packs</i>
<i>CE</i>	<i>Circular Economy</i>
<i>DfA</i>	<i>Design for Assembly</i>
<i>DfD</i>	<i>Design for Disassembly</i>
<i>GDPR</i>	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>KPI</i>	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Identity</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

MARBEL is a 3,5-year project with the aim of developing an innovative and competitive lightweight battery with increased energy density and shorter recharging times with the objective to accelerate the mass market take-up of electric vehicles.

The project innovation is based on the following main pillars:

- Advanced battery packaging using a Design for Assembly (DfA) and Disassembly (DfD) methodology.
- Lightweight and sustainable Battery Packaging.
- Solutions and processes for the sustainable dismantling and 2nd life
- Flexible advanced battery management systems.
- Ultra-Fast Charging strategies and enhanced thermal management
- Procedures for characterisation and validation of future performance and safety

FRAUNHOFER is the leader of **WP9 Exploitation and Dissemination** and Task 9.1. *Dissemination Activities*. On the other hand, Eurecat is the partner leader of the Task 9.4 *Communication Activities*. Together FRAUNHOFER and EUT are responsible for defining the project's Communication and Dissemination Plan.

The MARBEL Communication and Dissemination Plan has the objective to **raise awareness** on the project main goals and activities, **exploit and disseminate the project results and activities** to as many relevant actors as possible, **divulge the project results to target audiences** to **support exploitation** and ensure market uptake, **share the know-how generated** from the project with the scientific and industrial community and support all project activities and training the next generation of researchers and industry professionals.

This document compiles the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, including the creation and maintenance of the project's website, social media channels and posts, the creation of promotional materials, press releases, scientific publications, the organization of workshops, training activities and stakeholder engagement events and attendance to strategic conferences, fairs, congresses and other events.

This deliverable also includes the dissemination objectives, key messages, target audiences and timing of activities. Key performance indicators (KPIs) for each communication and dissemination activity will be defined and reported, ensuring the traceability of the activities that are not listed under particular deliverables or milestones.

1. Communication and dissemination plan

The main goals of the MARBEL project communication and dissemination strategy are:

- Increase the global visibility of MARBEL and its outcomes in Europe and beyond
- Develop novel communication and dissemination activities to facilitate knowledge transfer to scientific and industry stakeholders
- Raise awareness on the need to move towards sustainable transport.
- Showcase the potential of new batteries and make them available for uptake by the European automotive industry and global markets

It is worth noting that in order to protect the commercial interests of the partners, the publication of the materials will be selective, except for submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners decide which part of the projects' information is to be protected by copyright or trade secrets and which part of the information is suitable for disseminating widely.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project dissemination¹.

1.1 Target of communication and dissemination

An initial analysis of the dissemination target audiences has been done. Four stakeholder groups have been identified as target audience of the communication and dissemination activities, including: academia, industry, end-users / customers, policy makers and the society at large. Detailed information is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Stakeholder groups

The process of identifying the key persons and entities that embody this stakeholder consideration has already begun. A list of target contacts for all communication and dissemination activities is

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding_guide/grants/grantmanagement/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

under development. For this specific purpose, EUT and FW-IWU have prepared an excel file to record the stakeholders identified (containing just the name of the organization, country and activity and without including personal information details) which is stored in the MARBEL internal collaborative platform.

A form inviting stakeholders to sign-up for the project mailing list has been circulated and registered participants are automatically added to the list of dissemination contacts.

1.2 Channels

For communication and dissemination activities, the MARBEL project will use a wide range of channels and actions, ranging from social media activity, media relations, promotional materials to scientific publications, organization of workshops and specific stakeholder engagement events, and presentation of the project in key events.

Besides the aforementioned project channels, all partners will make use of their own channels (websites, presence on Social Media and corporate newsletters / publications) to disseminate news about MARBEL and reach a broader audience.

Figure 2: MARBEL Communication and Dissemination channels

1.3 Key messages

The communication and dissemination plan messages have been carefully designed and tailored with each of the stakeholders defined and will be adapted to the different MARBEL communication and dissemination channels. The messages go together with the main dissemination and communication objectives and translate the possibilities and strength of the research and development done during the project.

The following messages will be evolved in pertinent messages for all audiences, both specialized and non-specialized, in a way that they can understand actions and results of MARBEL project.

The general messages that MARBEL will address to stakeholders include:

- MARBEL will develop a new light, modular, versatile and high-performant battery pack for Electric Vehicles with increased energy density and allowing higher range and shorter recharging times.
- MARBEL will develop and advanced modular Battery Management System with innovative wireless communications, remote maintenance and self-updating capabilities.
- MARBEL research will allow the modularity of battery packs and increase the battery lifetime, its recyclability, and reconditioning of its components for a 2nd life application.
- MARBEL will develop and implement future innovative and efficient test procedures which include the versatile eVIL (Electric vehicle-in the-loop) suitable for all vehicle segments, as well as Artificial Intelligence.
- MARBEL project contributes to meet the EU emission reduction target of 40% by 2030 by developing more efficient batteries for Electric Vehicles.
- MARBEL is funded by the EU to boost the penetration and usage of Electric Vehicles in EU member states.

For each stakeholder groups, MARBEL dissemination and communication activities will transmit the following messages highlighting the benefits of MARBEL project for them and their needs. Messages will be updated and evolved during project execution.

Academia

- MARBEL project will advance the state-of-the-art in battery design and processes (Housing, cell-to-cell electrical connections and design for dis-/assembly), in Advanced BMS functionalities, and in Ultra-fast charging and Thermal management strategies.
- Some of the results of MARBEL project will be openly available to academia supporting further research activities.
- MARBEL to reinforce the availability of a pool of skills in Europe in battery eco-design, novel battery management systems functionalities, dismantling and reconditioning strategies.
- New manufacturing techniques and materials research in aluminium will be studied both for the housing and as the heat exchanger.

Industry

- MARBEL will design a modular, sustainable and lightweight Battery Pack focusing the design on further dismantling, life enlargement and second use.
- The project will develop a standardised and scalable battery management system that can be easily adapted to different types of cells, batteries, manufactures and to any battery size for different applications (such as, for example, Light and Heavy-duty vehicles).

- MARBEL development allows a single cell replacement being an advantage when in presence of cell fault and 2nd life batteries.
- MARBEL will provide a new simulation methodology capable to predict battery performance and maintenance.
- MARBEL is boosting the appearance and consolidation of new players and business models on the European market, especially SMEs.
- MARBEL will develop and implement future innovative and efficient test procedures which include the versatile eVIL (Electric vehicle-in the-loop) suitable for all vehicle segments, as well as Artificial Intelligence.

Consumers and end-users

- MARBEL will provide electric vehicles users batteries with a lifespan on 300,000 km, almost doubling the lifespan of current batteries in the market.
- Electric vehicles with MARBEL batteries will have a shorter recharging time than current solutions in the market (-25 %).
- MARBEL solution will decrease users' range anxiety by avoiding unforeseen battery failures and better prediction of battery performance.

Policy markers

- The project will reinforce the European position in the global battery market and contribute to environmental and societal targets.
- MARBEL will contribute to foster the creation and use of European Technology Infrastructures dedicated to the Battery Pack of the future.
- The project contributes to the New Industrial Strategy for Europe, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Regulatory Framework for Sustainable Batteries part of key actions of the European Green Deal.
- MARBEL results can lead to an increased attractiveness of Europe for the battery manufacturers and related businesses, contributing to recovering European leaderships in this sector.

Society at large

- MARBEL project will support the EU automotive sector in the widespread penetration of electric vehicles.
- MARBEL project contributes to meet the EU emission reduction target of 40% by 2030 by developing more efficient batteries for Electric Vehicles.
- MARBEL contributes to produce more sustainable and efficient electric batteries.
- The uptake of electric vehicles with lithium-ion batteries will produce millions of batteries no longer maintaining the power for electric vehicles but maintaining the 80% of its capacity. MARBEL project will establish a protocol for the reuse of the battery and 2nd life.

2. Communication and dissemination management

2.1 Distribution of responsibilities

The MARBEL dissemination and communication strategy foresees the active involvement and commitment of all project partners for presenting the project and its outcomes.

WP9 Exploitation and dissemination includes the following tasks related to communication and dissemination:

- **Task 9.1** – Dissemination management (FH-IWU, all partners)
- **Task 9.3** – Clustering with other initiatives (FH-IWU, EUT, CRF, all partners)
- **Task 9.4** – Communication activities (EUT, all partners)

FH-IWU is the Communication and Dissemination lead beneficiary, responsible for coordinating WP9 activities, ensuring the proper information exchange within the consortium and supporting the full dissemination of the project and its results. In addition, FH-IWU will lead the creation of synergies with relevant projects and initiatives of interest.

EUT, through its Research Communication Office (RCO), will be the partner directly responsible for the development of the project's visual identity and website, the production of communication and PR materials and the creation of content for project's social media accounts.

In addition, all partners will contribute to ensure the successful implementation of the communication and dissemination activities and the reach to the different stakeholder groups identified.

2.2 Requirements

All communication and dissemination materials produced in the project (posters, presentations, promotional material, publications, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format (e.g. social media) will display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement:

According to the Grant Agreement *“unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:*

- a) *Display the EU emblem*
- b) *Include the following text*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 963540.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right of exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark of logo, either by registration or by any other means.

In addition, results disseminated are recommended to include the following disclaimer:

[This result NAME] reflects only the author's view and the Agency / Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

2.3 Monitoring and reporting

2.3.1 Activities reporting

An Excel file has been prepared by FW-IWU and EUT to register all communication and dissemination activities done by partners during the project execution.

This file is located in the Sharepoint online repository that is available to all partners and contains a description of the activity, the target audience, date and location, the partners involved, the number of people reached, feedback received and information about which WP/Task was associated with the activity.

Table 1: Table to record the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners

Type of action	Primary audience reached with the action	Secondary audience reached	Title of the action	Location	Date	Number of people reached	Link	MARBEL attendees/organisers (if applicable)

2.3.2 Communication and dissemination activities KPIs

KPIs have been assigned to a number of communication and dissemination activities planned in the project in order to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project. Progress regarding project KPIs will be reported in WP9 deliverables (D9.1, D9.2 and D9.3), project meetings and project review reports. These are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: MARBEL Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M42
Website	Number of website visits	Website Analytics	>4,000
	Number of pages viewed		>15,000
	Number of users		>2,000
	Average session time		>1 min
Social Media	Twitter: Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	>100
	Twitter: Number of tweets		>150
	Twitter: Twitter impressions		>30,000
	Twitter: Likes on tweets		>50
	Twitter: Retweets		>30
	Twitter: Mentions		>20
	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	>10
YouTube: Number of video views	>500		

Press Releases	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>4
	Articles published in EU outlets		>20
Events	Number of events participated (congresses, conferences, etc.)	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>20
	Number of workshops with OEMs and Tier1/2		2
	Number of workshops with the advisory board		>2
	Number of workshops organised with other CollaBat and BAT-10 projects		2
	Number of workshops participated / organised with EU clusters, associations (EARPA, VDA, ELCA)		2
	Number of webinars organised		3
Publications	Number of scientific publications	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	8
	Number of articles in specialised magazines / outlets		3
Direct dissemination actions	Number of meetings with OEMs, Tier1/2 and SMEs	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	30
	Number of meetings with EV user associations		5
Visual Materials	Number of posters produced	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	4
	Number of infosheets produced		1
	Audio-visual materials		>10
	Number of roll-ups		1
	Number of brochures		1

2.3.3 KPIs reporting

The progress of KPIs until the end of the project will be reported in project. In addition, to facilitate the reporting, an Excel file has been prepared to record the monthly progress of KPIs.

The file is stored in the shared WP9 folder (accessible by all partners) and includes the following sections:

- **Web and Social Media:** to report the progress on project and partner channels

Table 3: Website and social media analytics reporting table

KPIs Channels	MARBEL	Digital	jan-2021	feb-21	mar-21	apr-2021	may-21	Jun-2021	Jul-2021
			M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7
Twitter Corporate Account									
# Followers									

# New Followers							
# Total Tweets							
# New Tweets							
# Twitter Impressions							
# Mentions							
# Likes on Tweets							
# Retweets							
Twitter Accounts Partners							
TOTAL All partners							
# Tweets							
# Likes							
# Retweets							
LinkedIn - Partners Accounts							
TOTAL (aggregate)							
# Posts							
# Likes							
# Comments							
# Shares							
Facebook Partners							
TOTAL							
# Posts							
# Likes							
# Comments							
# Shares							
Social Media Posts Partners (SUM)							
# Posts	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
# Likes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
# Shares / Retweets	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Web (MATOMO Analytics)							
# Web Visits	NA	NA	NA				
Avg. session time	NA	NA	NA				
# Pages Viewed	NA	NA	NA				
# Users	NA	NA	NA				

- **Scientific papers:** for tracking on-going and published papers

Table 4: Table to report scientific publications

Type of scientific publication	Title of the scientific publication	DOI	ISSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent
[Article in journal]		-			

[Conference proceeding /workshop]					
[Books/ Monographies]					
[Chapter in Books]					

Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year	Relevant pages	Peer-review	Is/Will open access
					YES / NO	YES / NO

- **Media Clipping:** for recording articles in general and specialised media outlets

Table 5: Media Clipping table

ONLINE						
Date	Media	Title	Audience	Economic Value	Link	
PRINT						
Date	Media	Title	Readers	Circulation	Economic Value	Link
TOTAL	# of articles					
2021						
2022						
2023						
2024						

2.3.4 Risks and mitigation measures

The early risks associated to communication and dissemination, as well as the contingency plans foreseen, are presented to ensure that adverse situations are properly managed along the evolution of the project. In the following graph a schematic representation of the MARBEL risk process is shown.

Figure 3: Risk management process

The exposure to a given risk is estimated using the risk matrix as following:

Impact \ Probability	1- Extremely unlikely	2- Likely	3- Extremely likely
1- Not critical	1	2	3
2- Significant	2	4	6
3- Fundamental to coninuing operations	3	6	9

Risk score = Impact x Probability Priority: ■ High ■ Medium ■ Low

Figure 4: Risk management matrix

The risks faced in the completion of activities planned in WP6 and potential mitigation measures have been defined and are presented in Table 6. This table will be reviewed periodically to spot any new risks and determine if there is a need to put in place mitigation actions.

Table 6: Risks and mitigation measures

Risks	Probability	Impact	Risk score	Mitigation measures
Low stakeholder engagement in webinars, workshops and local sessions	2	2	4 Medium	Intensive communication campaigns promoting the activities through relevant channels will be run minimum 2 months in advance. Take advantage of project partners involved in relevant EU projects and initiatives to serve as ambassadors of MARBEL and

				multiply project dissemination and stakeholder engagement.
Not enough dissemination opportunities due to COVID-19 effects	2	2	4 Medium	Thorough identification of activities and organisation of own events. Stronger emphasis on the organisation of online project activities (such as webinars) and possibility to accommodate initially planned physical activities remotely. Higher reliance on online channels (e.g. social media). Transferring actions planned for presence fairs to digital versions.
Not enough engagement on MARBEL communication channels	1	2	2 Low	Creation of more content for the project website and social media that engages stakeholders, increase the frequency of publication on project channels. Provision and collection of free to use pictures, videos and data for social media actions in MARBEL-SharePoint folder.
Low project visibility	1	2	2 Low	Develop an appealing website and communication materials. Organise joint activities with other initiatives and projects. Regular check of publication activities containing trade fair and conference participation, publications and social media activities guaranteeing the visibility. Increase of efforts on audio/visual material for extensive use on web platforms (e.g. YouTube). Search engine optimization to increase hit rate of website.

3. Communication and dissemination tools and activities

3.1 Project branding and templates

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing MARBEL’s official Visual Corporate Image (VCI), aimed at **properly aligning all communication materials across all the tasks of the project.**

The project branding is essential to create and establish MARBEL’s identity, as well as to give a consistent and coherent image of the project. **It is important to use the elements established properly and only employ the authorised documents templates in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand and do it consistently.**

The sections hereinafter describe the different project branding elements designed, including the project’s logo, corporate colours, fonts, templates and graphic elements to be used and implemented in all communication and dissemination tasks by all project’s partners.

3.1.1 MARBEL logo

The logo is the main brand element of the visual identity of MARBEL and has the objective to represent the different concepts surrounding the project.

As pictured in the following figures, the MARBEL logo includes the acronym of the project and the colours established in the corporate visual identity manual, being the green the main colour of the logotype. Additionally, the project logo shape symbolises the charge of an electric battery and includes the figure of a car with the objective to represent the concept of electric vehicles, one of the main topics of MARBEL.

Different versions of the logo have been created: a full colour logo, a positive and negative black and white logo, and a version to be used in the main project colour background.

Figure 5: Full Colour logo and logo version with colour background

Figure 6: Black and white logo version negative/positive

3.1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards guidebook has been produced and distributed among partners to ensure that the project's branding is not compromised, and all partners use the elements properly in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand.

The visual identity manual defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to MARBEL including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and other graphic resources. Additionally, it sets a design layout for project promotional and communication materials to be developed in following months. All the consortium should treat the guidebook as a source of the materials and instructions and as a basis for further development of project materials.

The following sections describe some parts included in the manual.

3.1.2.1 Corporate colours

This section presents the MARBEL main colours palette that must be used in all project materials, such as the website, social media channels and other promotional or graphic elements.

According to the palette designed, the main colours of MARBEL project are E-Green (Pantone: #0FD600) and E-Black (Pantone: #000000), complemented with two gradients: E-Gray (15% of E-Black) and a combination between the E-Green and E-black colour.

Figure 7: MARBEL project colours

3.1.2.2 Fonts

The Visual Corporate Image manual also establishes two types of fonts to be used for project internal and external documents and materials.

Montserrat is the special font used for promotional and advertising materials. This type of font and its different versions are free, and partners can download them in [Google Fonts page here](https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat?query=montserrat).

<p><small>Text Font for promotional items Available at: https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat?query=montserrat</small></p>	<p>Montserrat Light abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Montserrat Light Italic</i> abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>
<p>Montserrat Regular</p>	<p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Montserrat Regular Italic</i> abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>
<p>Montserrat Bold</p>	<p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Montserrat Bold Italic</i> abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>

Figure 8: Use of fonts for promotional materials

On the other hand, **Arial** and its different versions are the main font established for deliverables and internal documents because it is a standard Microsoft Office included in Word and PowerPoint documents, among others.

Fonts

Text Font
for deliverables
and internal
documents **only**

Arial Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Arial Bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Arial Italic

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Figure 9: Use of fonts for internal documents and deliverables

3.1.2.3 Stationery

The MARBEL Visual Corporate Image manual includes different elements designed for stationery materials, such as **letters, envelopes, business cards, the image of the project for digital supports and applications and other internal and external documents**, that partners could use when it is needed.

Figure 10: View of stationery materials

3.1.2.4 Graphic resources

This section explains the different graphic items that can be used for the design of promotional materials, external and internal project presentations or other documents. **These elements have been broadly used for the design of project Word and Power Point templates, as well as headers for the project’s Twitter profile.**

Figure 11: MARBEL graphic resources

3.1.2.5 Social Media headers

The Visual Corporate Image manual also includes two different Twitter header templates to be used. One of them has been already used and integrated in the project’s profile.

Figure 12: Two versions of Twitter header templates

3.1.3 Templates

Different document templates have been prepared and shared with all project's partners. A Power Point template has been produced for internal and external presentations, as well as four different Word documents: one for deliverables, one for meeting's agenda, one for letters or other purposes and another one to be used for minutes.

These template documents will be used throughout all the project's execution to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

3.1.3.1 Power point presentation template

A Power Point template has been designed to be used for all project's internal and external presentations.

This document presents a variety of slides with different options to include the text and different visual elements to be used and adapted by all partners when preparing an internal project's presentation.

In the following figure it is shown a screenshot of some slides:

Figure 13: View of MARBEL presentation template

3.1.3.2 Deliverable template

A Word document template has been created and shared with partners to be used for all project's deliverables.

This template establishes the use of a page header with the project's logo and the funding body's logo and a footer with some information about the document and a graphic element created for project materials.

Other aspects included in the deliverable template are specified here:

Title is the chapter title.

Normal Text is ARIAL 10pt, single line spacing and justified.

Titles Text is ARIAL 15pt, in main project colour (Pantone: #0FD600)

Each section has to start at a new page.

Template for unordered lists: *(See an example of unordered list here)*

- Style bulleted – To be used with bullets (unordered lists). Don't change the bullets unless absolutely necessary.
- Style bulleted – 2nd Level of bullets
- Style bulleted – 3rd Level of bullets

It's important to have a template for ordered lists too: *(See an example of ordered list here)*

1. The style is called Numbered bullet and it follows the same rules as the unordered list.
 - i. The 2nd Level of the ordered list uses Latin numbering.
 - a. The 3rd Level of the ordered list uses the alphabet.

Figure 14: View of some deliverable template pages

3.1.3.3 Agenda template

The template designed for the agenda presents a header page with MARBEL and its funding body's logo and a footer with some information and a graphic element pertaining to project's branding resources.

The font used for title in agenda's document is **Arial 16pt, bold and in main project corporate colour** and for the normal text is also **Arial 11pt, single line spacing and justified**.

AGENDA MEETING

Date: XXXX/XXXX

Venue: Eurecat

Time	Topic	Presenter/Facilitator
09:30 - 09:45	Welcome and introductions	EUT
09:45 - 10:30	WP1	EUT
10:30 - 11:15	WP2	
11:15 - 11:45	Coffee Break	
11:45 - 13:15	WP3	EUT
13:15 - 14:45	Lunch	
14:45 - 15:45	WP4, WP5, WP6	EUT
19:00	Evening meal	All

Resources:
Lap top, Wi fi access, Projector, PowerPoint, presentations.

Special notes and information:

Venue
Accommodation
Every partner is responsible for their own accommodation booking.
Transportation

MARBEL Agenda Template Page 1 of 2

Figure 15: MARBEL agenda template

3.1.3.4 Meeting minutes template

This template will be used to present the minutes and the list of attendants to an internal project meeting. The document includes a header page with the MARBEL and funding body’s logos and a footer with some information and a graphic element.

For general title of the document it has been used the font **Arial 16pt, bold and in main corporate green colour and for the normal text is Arial 11pt.**

Figure 16: Snapchat of MARBEL minutes' template

3.1.3.5 Letter template

This template is specifically designed for letters that consortium partners may need to write during the project. It includes some lines for the details of the sender and reference to MARBEL project. Text is **Arial 11pt**.

Figure 17: MARBEL letter template

3.2 Website

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing the official MARBEL project website. The registered URL is www.marbel-project.eu .

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. **The website will be the anchor for all communication and dissemination activities** related to the project and will serve as a central point of entry for all public material, including the project’s basic information, expected impacts and objectives. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active at least during three years after the project’s finalisation to support the exploitation of project outputs.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project and it gives access to MARBEL social media channels (Twitter so far).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System (CMS) has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat proposes to use Wordpress, as the Eurecat’s Research Communications Office has wide experience with this CMS.

Regarding the website languages, the basis is English but if a need to translate some parts of the website arise, a multilingual plugin will be installed for this purpose.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

3.2.1 Website structure

The following information architecture for MARBEL website is proposed in the figure below. In green you can see the pages /structure that have been created for the website launch, while, in black, the pages that will be developed afterwards, in line with project advances.

Further changes to the website structure may be made in the future to allocate documents and dissemination actions, as well as to support specific WP or tasks.

Figure 18: Website structure

3.2.2 Website content

The texts hereinafter describe the contents published on the first version of the website.

3.2.2.1 Homepage

It includes two sliders: “**Design, manufacturing and validation of the next generation of battery packs for the automotive mass-market**” and “**Circular economy approach in Electric Vehicles battery packs**”

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, its main objectives and key outputs, as well as a section on the context.

In addition, a section mentioning the consortium linking to the partners page has been designed and included in the homepage.

As soon as the “News & Events” sections have some new articles and contents, a section at the homepage showing the latest publications, together with the project’s twitter feed will be created. Specific sections will be created to promote and divulge the platform and information services that will be created during the project.

MARBEL in a nutshell

The MARBEL project develops an **innovative and competitive lightweight battery** with the objective to accelerate the mass market take-up of electric and hybrid vehicles.

MARBEL will design, develop and demonstrate a new compact, modular, weight-optimised and high-performance battery pack with longer life, greater energy efficiency in charging and energy use based on a robust and flexible battery management system (BMS) along with ultra-fast battery charging and cooling. Modularity will make possible to streamline repair, servicing and recycling processes, while preserving the value of new batteries and reducing hazards for operators and environmental impact.

BUTTON– FIND OUT MORE – link to “About MARBEL”

Pillars

- [ICON] Advanced battery packs using a Design for Assembly and Disassembly methodology
- [ICON] Lightweight and sustainable Battery Packaging
- [ICON] Solutions and processes for the sustainable dismantling and 2nd life
- [ICON] Flexible advanced battery management systems
- [ICON] Ultra-fast charging strategies and enhanced thermal management for a extended useful battery life
- [ICON] Procedures for characterisation and validation of future performance and safety

Aligned with EU needs and policies

Contributing to solving industry and societal challenges

- **More sustainable and efficient electric batteries**
MARBEL will provide electric vehicles' users batteries with a lifespan on 300,000 km, almost doubling the lifespan of current batteries in the market.

Electric vehicles with MARBEL batteries will have a shorter recharging time than current solutions in the market (-25 %).

- **Aligned with EU policies**

The project contributes to the New Industrial Strategy for Europe, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Regulatory Framework for Sustainable Batteries part of key actions of the European Green Deal.

- **Contribution to meet GHG EU emission target**

MARBEL project contributes to meet the EU emission reduction target of 40% by 2030 by developing more efficient batteries for Electric Vehicles.

Quote

The project aims at fostering the acceptance and use of electric vehicles by solving two of the main critical points in consumer's decision-making: limited vehicle autonomy and charging time, enabling travelling longer distances.

- Alberto Gómez, Head of Eurecat's Electric Mobility and Energy Storage research line and MARBEL technical coordinator

Contact us

Stay in touch!

Subscribe to our community of interest to be informed about the latest news and developments of MARBEL project

BUTTON– SUBSCRIBE NOW – link to “Subscription form”

News & events

This section will include a Twitter widget and will show the latest news and events published on the website.

Partners

MARBEL interdisciplinary consortium is made up of 16 partners from 8 European countries required for the development of the battery pack of the future.

6 research centres, 1 OEM, 2 Tier1, 3 Tier2, 1 automotive engineering company and 2 SMEs

LOGOS PARTNERS

BUTTON – KNOW THE WHOLE CONSORTIUM – Link to the “Consortium” page

Manufacturing the next generation of battery packs for the automotive mass-market

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

- H2020 project on Electric Vehicle batteries
- Advanced modular battery pack
- 300,000km lifespan batteries
- Collaborative project with 16 partners

MARBEL IN A NUTSHELL

Towards an environment-friendly and lightweight mobility

The MARBEL project develops an **innovative and competitive lightweight battery** with the objective to accelerate the mass market take-up of electric and hybrid vehicles.

MARBEL will **design, develop and demonstrate a new compact, modular, weight-optimised and high-performance battery pack** with longer life, greater energy efficiency in charging and energy use based on a **robust and flexible battery management system (BMS)** along with **ultra-fast battery charging and cooling**. Modularity will make possible to streamline repair, servicing and recycling processes, while preserving the value of new batteries and reducing hazards for operators and environmental impact.

[DISCOVER THE PROJECT](#)

PILLARS

MARBEL features

<p>2nd life reuse</p> <p>Solutions and processes for the sustainable dismantling and 2nd life</p>		
<p>Performance & safety</p> <p>Procedures for characterisation and validation of future performance and safety</p>		

ALIGNED WITH EUROPEAN NEEDS

Contributing to solving EU industry and societal challenges

+ More sustainable and efficient electric vehicles

MARBEL will provide electric vehicles' users batteries with a lifespan on 300,000 km, almost doubling the lifespan of current batteries in the market. Electric vehicles with MARBEL batteries will have a shorter recharging time than current solutions in the market (-25 %).

+ Aligned with EU policies

The project contributes to the [New Industrial Strategy for Europe](#), the [Circular Economy Action Plan](#) and the [Regulatory Framework for Sustainable Batteries](#) part of key actions of the European Green Deal.

+ Contribution to meet GHG EU emission targets

MARBEL project contributes to meet the EU emission reduction target of 40% by 2030 by developing more efficient batteries for Electric Vehicles.

“The project aims at fostering the acceptance and use of electric vehicles by solving two of the main critical points in consumer’s decision-making: limited vehicle autonomy and charging time, enabling travelling longer distances.

ALBERTO GÓMEZ
MARBEL technical coordinator
Head of Eurecat’s Electric Mobility and Energy Storage research line

Stay in touch!

Subscribe to our community of interest to be informed about the latest news and developments of MARBEL project

[SUBSCRIBE NOW](#)

Latest MARBEL updates!

EU consortium to produce more sustainable and efficient electric batteries

February 13, 2021

EU consortium to contribute to Marbel to produce more sustainable and efficient electric batteries The European Marbel consortium has the...

[Read more](#)

MARBEL project kicks-off!

February 4, 2021

MARBEL project kicks-off! The MARBEL project has kicked-off with the objective to design, manufacture and validate an innovative and competitive...

[Read more](#)

PARTNERS

Our team

MARBEL interdisciplinary consortium is made up of **16 partners** from **7 European countries** required for the development of the battery pack of the future.
The project is coordinated by **Eurecat Technology Center**.

ABOUT MARBEL TEAM 👥

6
research centers

1
OEM

6
Tier 1 and Tier 2 companies

2
SMEs

1
automotive engineering company

CONTACT INFO

Get in touch!

DROP US A LINE

We are looking forward to hear from you!

Name

Email

Message

I have read and I accept the [privacy information](#).

Send message

COORDINATOR INFORMATION

Eduard Piqueras
Project coordinator

Eurecat Technology Center, Spain

72, Bilbao Street
08005, Barcelona

EMAIL
info@marbel-project.eu

Tweets by [Marbel_H2020](#)

Figure 19: View of MARBEL homepage designed - <https://marbel-project.eu>

3.2.2.2 About MARBEL

3.2.2.2.1 The project

Manufacturing and assembly of modular and reusable Electric Vehicle battery for environment-friendly and lightweight mobility

MARBEL focuses on the need for fast charging and long-lasting batteries to boost end-user demands, while applying high modularity and easy assembly and developing novel testing methodologies.

The project will design, develop and demonstrate new modular, compact, lightweight and high-performance battery packs together with flexible and robust battery management systems for battery electric vehicles and plug-in hybrids, while maintaining safety levels, allowing fast, high quality and cost-effective large-scale production and following ecodesign principles.

MARBEL modules, easy to pack together and to disassemble, are expected to ease the manufacturing and dismantling of different battery configurations sharing the same production process and common elements. MARBEL will develop and qualify future and innovative performance- and safety- related test procedures of developed functionalities such as the use of miniaturised housings, a flexible test-bench simulating integration electric vehicle conditions (electric Vehicle In-the-Loop) and artificial intelligence as a tool to reduce the time of laboratory experiments.

The project concepts, starting at TRL4 from results obtained in previous projects, aim to reach an average of TRL7-8 with new developments tested and demonstrated in operational environment.

Start date: 1 January 2021 – 30 June 2024

Duration: 42 months

Funded under: Horizon 2020 programme – H2020-EU.3.4

Phases

1. **MARBEL requirements set up**
Setup the requirements for safety, modularity, 2nd use, performance and ecodesign.
2. **Development of solutions and components**
Design of the charging station, upscaling the thermal management system and BMS prediction and maintenance actions.
3. **Battery manufacturing, assembly and dismantling**
Feasibility studies, Design for Manufacturing and Design for Assembly activities, module and battery pack assembly, integration in the electric vehicle-in-the-loop and dismantling operations.
4. **Validation and demonstration of the results expected from the project**
Development and definition of innovative performance and safety related test procedures, 2nd life applications addressed and demonstrated.

Expected results

- **Electric Vehicle Battery Pack:** Demonstration of a complete battery pack, subcomponents, ultra-fast charging and thermal system at electric-vehicle-in-the-loop level
- **Battery Management System:** Battery management system, smart cell manager and wireless communications integrated in the battery pack

- **Failure prediction and maintenance:** Advanced estimation algorithms verified for predicting early failure
- **2nd Life applications:** Testing of 2nd life applications in microgrid environment
- **Modules demonstration:** Demonstration of modules and battery pack fully assembled and dismantling

R&D beyond the state of the art

Advanced battery packs and materials

Implementation of a dismantling and refurbishment process of the battery during design. Design for Disassembly (DfD) methodology will enable a sustainable battery pack ready for 2nd use and dismantling. In MARBEL's first stage, a dismantling and modularity protocol will be created covering aspects such as safety, modularity, second use, recyclability and ecodesign.

Lightweight and sustainable Battery Packaging

MARBEL will focus on lightweighting the housing and most of the metallic parts of a battery pack. The project will ecodesign an optimised cost-effective housing based on recycled aluminium extruded profiles, using innovative simulation techniques to optimise the material quantity for the housing.

Solutions and processes for the sustainable dismantling and 2nd life

The current recycling processes of battery packs are not profitable, being very expensive energetically, while there is still not a clear availability of efficient technologies in recycling. MARBEL proposes a testing and classification standard development for used batteries, focused on analysing and determining their suitability in 2nd life applications.

Modular and flexible battery management systems

Current battery management systems solutions impose longer development time for battery systems since they must be fully developed for each application. MARBEL approach consists of developing a battery management system that is not tailored to any specific battery and that can be adapted to a large variety of cells, modules and batteries with different sizes, voltages and capacity.

Ultra-fast charging strategies and enhanced thermal management

Efforts in electric vehicles charging industry have been focused in reducing charging times whilst maintaining high efficiency and safety. MARBEL will develop a charging station prepared for high-power charging and the development of an innovative thermal management system to cool battery cells more efficiently.

Procedures for characterisation and validation of future performance and safety

MARBEL aims to improve state-of-the-art test procedures reducing time and cost while improving the quality and quantity of knowledge gathered about different systems. This will be achieved by the implementation of testing at early stages, data processing with AI, the validation of a mechanic behaviour of novel housing with a miniaturised version and the validation of the system performance at full scale.

About the project

Home / About the project

MARBEL PROJECT

Manufacturing and assembly of modular and reusable Electric Vehicle battery for environment-friendly and lightweight mobility

MARBEL focuses on the need for fast charging and long-lasting batteries to boost end-user demands, while applying high modularity and easy assembly and developing novel testing methodologies.

The project will design, develop and demonstrate new modular, compact, lightweight and high-performance battery packs together with flexible and robust battery management systems for battery electric vehicles and plug-in hybrids, while maintaining safety levels, allowing fast, high quality and cost-effective large-scale production and following ecodesign principles.

MARBEL modules, easy to pack together and to disassemble, are expected to ease the manufacturing and dismantling of different battery configurations sharing the same production process and common elements. MARBEL will develop and qualify future and innovative performance- and safety- related test procedures of developed functionalities such as the use of miniaturised housings, a flexible test-bench simulating integration electric vehicle conditions (electric Vehicle In-the-Loop) and artificial intelligence as a tool to reduce the time of laboratory experiments.

The project concepts, starting at TRL4 from results obtained in previous projects, aim to reach an average of TRL7-8 with new developments tested and demonstrated in operational environment.

Start - end date

1 January 2021 – 30 June 2024

Duration

42 months

Funded under

Horizon 2020 programme – H2020-EU.3.4

Project phases

01. MARBEL requirements set up

Setup the requirements for safety, modularity, 2nd use, performance and ecodesign

02. Development of solutions and components

Design of the charging station, upscaling the thermal management system and BMS prediction and maintenance actions

03. Battery manufacturing, assembly and dismantling

Feasibility studies, Design for Manufacturing and Design for Assembly activities, module and battery pack assembly, integration in the electric vehicle-in-the-loop and dismantling operations

04. Validation and demonstration

Development and definition of innovative performance and safety related test procedures, 2nd life applications addressed and demonstrated

OUTPUTS

Expected results

- ✓ **Electric Vehicle Battery Pack**
Demonstration of a complete battery pack, subcomponents, ultra-fast charging and thermal system at electric-vehicle-in-the-loop level
- ✓ **Battery management system**
Battery management system, smart cell manager and wireless communications integrated in the battery pack
- ✓ **Failure prediction and maintenance**
Advanced estimation algorithms verified for predicting early failure
- ✓ **2nd life applications**
Testing of 2nd life applications in microgrid environment
- ✓ **Modules demonstration**
Demonstration of modules and battery pack fully assembled and dismantling

RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT

Beyond the state of the art

01. Advanced battery packs and materials

Implementation of a dismantling and refurbishment process of the battery during design. Design for Disassembly (DFD) methodology will enable a sustainable battery pack ready for 2nd use and dismantling. In MARBEL's first stage, a dismantling and modularity protocol will be created covering aspects such as safety, modularity, second use, recyclability and ecodesign.

02. Lightweight and sustainable Battery Packaging

MARBEL will focus on lightweighting the housing and most of the metallic parts of a battery pack. The project will ecodesign an optimised cost-effective housing based on recycled aluminium extruded profiles, using innovative simulation techniques to optimise the material quantity for the housing.

03. Solutions and processes for a sustainable dismantling and 2nd life

The current recycling processes of battery packs are not profitable, being very expensive energetically, while there is still not a clear availability of efficient technologies in recycling. MARBEL proposes a testing and classification standard development for used batteries, focused on analysing and determining their suitability in 2nd life applications.

04. Modular and flexible battery management systems

Current battery management systems solutions impose longer development time for battery systems since they must be fully developed for each application. MARBEL approach consists of developing a battery management system that is not tailored to any specific battery and that can be adapted to a large variety of cells, modules and batteries with different sizes, voltages and capacity.

05. Ultra-fast charging strategies and enhanced thermal management

Efforts in electric vehicles charging industry have been focused in reducing charging times whilst maintaining high efficiency and safety. MARBEL will develop a charging station prepared for high-power charging and the development of an innovative thermal management system to cool battery cells more efficiently.

06. Procedures for characterisation and validation of future performance and safety

MARBEL aims to improve state-of-the-art test procedures reducing time and cost while improving the quality and quantity of knowledge gathered about different systems. This will be achieved by the implementation of testing at early stages, data processing with AI, the validation of a mechanic behaviour of novel housing with a miniaturised version and the validation of the system performance at full scale.

Figure 20: View of "About the project" page - <https://marbel-project.eu/about-marbel/>

3.2.2.3 Partners

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information. This page includes a first section with a brief description of the consortium, followed by a portfolio with the logos of the different partners, leading to a specific page per partners with their contact details.

MARBEL is a collaborative project with a multidisciplinary team with differential capacities and knowledge in disciplines ranging from automotive, battery development and energy management, to lightweight materials, ecodesign and circular economy. The consortium of the Marbel project is formed by 16 partners from Spain, Italy, France, Denmark, Turkey, Germany, Norway and Greece.

Figure 21: View of partners page - <https://marbel-project.eu/partners/>

Eurecat

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The center offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume

of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to MARBEL

Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project and leading the design for the battery pack ecodesign and materials, simplifying the standard performance experimental test procedures, as and assessing the economic and environmental benefits of the solution developed. We are also responsible for managing IPR and the project's communication activities.

Figure 22: Example of individual partners' pages

Agrati

Agrati is worldwide leader in special fastener solutions and components for the automotive sector with 12 production plants, 15 Sales & Application Offices, 5 logistics centres, more than 2.300 employees and a turnover of 517M€ in 2020.

Agrati boasts 4 Tech Centres for industrial R&I, supported by cutting edge laboratory equipments and software for engineering, co-design, testing & prototyping.

Every year Agrati purchases over 170.000 tons of steel, develops 850 new products, invests 8% in innovation and technology and produces 8 billion parts in order to assemble over 60 million cars all over the world.

Contribution to MARBEL

Agrati will design and produce fastening solutions for the assembly and disassembly of battery packs, with particular attention to the innovative smart solutions to connect and disconnect the cells together.

Agrati will be responsible for the procurement of all fasteners to produce MARBEL battery packs and it will contribute to the drafting and dissemination of guidelines and standards for the adoption on the European territory of the solutions that will be developed.

Fraunhofer-IWU

The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft is the world's largest organization for applied research. With a focus on smart manufacturing technologies, factory planning, digitisation in manufacturing and circular economy innovations, along many publicly-funded projects, Fraunhofer IWU is R&D partner for industry clients mainly from automotive, aerospace, mechanical engineering and tool and plant making industries. Over 600 staff are active in more than 1100 projects per year.

Contribution to MARBEL

Fraunhofer IWU is engaged in thermal management and housing of the batteries based upon metal foams and Phase Change Material taking care of mechanical and thermal protection of the system. Additionally, Fraunhofer IWU is Work Package Leader for Dissemination in the project.

IDIADA

IDIADA is a leading company specializing in providing design, engineering, testing and homologation services to the automotive industry worldwide.

Aiming at being up-to-date in innovation, research and development, IDIADA counts on cutting-edge technology in facilities and equipment. More than 2.800 engineers and technical profiles (Physicists, Mathematicians, etc) are developing, researching and innovating within this working environment.

The core services IDIADA provides are: Engineering, Proving Ground and Homologation. Main fields of engineering activity are power train, emissions, noise & vibration, vehicle dynamics, electronics & communications, fatigue & durability and active and passive safety.

Contribution to MARBEL

IDIADA is in charge of leading and executing different tasks related to the thermal management and Ultra-Fast charging strategies. IDIADA is also in charge of developing the Electric Vehicle in the Loop (EViL) test bench and performing different performance test of the battery.

ICCS

ICCS is a leading Greek research institute active in all diverse aspects of computer and telecommunications systems and their applications. ICCS is associated with the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the National Technical University of Athens. Since its establishment in 1989, ICCS has become a top tier research institute employing in excess of 500 highly skilled young engineers and scientists and collaborating with top-ranked universities, research organizations and industry in Europe and worldwide.

Contribution to MARBEL

Within MARBEL the Information Management Unit of ICCS will develop innovative Artificial Intelligence-based predictions for the computation of critical battery variables such as State of Charge, State of Health, etc.

IREC

The Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC) contribute to the sustainable development of society and enhance corporate competitiveness via the innovation and the development of new

technological products, mid- and long-term research and the dissemination of scientific knowledge to citizens.

The Institute is a centre of excellence and an international benchmark organization in the energy field through research, development and innovation, working in coordination with the administration, the industry and the academia.

Contribution to MARBEL

IREC contributes to MARBEL with the development of a flexible advanced battery management system with enhanced functionalities aimed to improve the battery operation and its safety. Its flexible architecture yields a system adaptable to several cell chemistries and different battery pack size and voltage, thus, applicable to a large range of electric mobility solutions.

PTS Power Tech Systems

PTS is a French company specialized in design and engineering of high-performance Lithium-Ion batteries (> 1KW) covering a large application spectrum (vehicle traction, stationary storage, Off-Grid, etc.).

With over 15 years' experience in this field, we have developed a high level of expertise to satisfy our customers and our battery systems are designed to be innovative, scalable, compact, lightweight and reliable. This leads us to be constantly at the cutting edge of technology.

The batteries PTS people (Engineers, Business, Assembly line and supply chain) produce to solve new challenges are currently running for Marine traction, Agricultural robot, Solar/Wind Off Grid systems and many other sectors around the World.

Contribution to MARBEL

PowerTech is in charge of leading the development of Battery Pack functional requirements and guidelines. These guidelines will serve as inputs for the development of other activities associated with the project.

We will also contribute to deliver a description of the Battery Management Systems (BMS) architecture and functionalities for the 1st and 2nd life application.

THI

The University of Applied Sciences Ingolstadt (THI) was established in 1994 and offers excellent learning and working conditions for 150 professors, 700 employees and over 6000 students.

Besides high-quality practical oriented education, THI is highly committed towards research and development. Applied research is carried out through both publically funded and industry-financed projects. With its research center CARISSMA, a strong research focus is on enhancing vehicle safety. The CARISSMA Institute of Electric, Connected and Secure Mobility (C-ECOS) thereby focuses on safe electromobility and accident research as well as Car2X-communications and Automotive IT-Security.

Contribution to MARBEL

THI is in charge of leading the testing, demonstration and validation of the developed system. We additionally contribute to the definition of the system's requirements (especially safety) and to the development of the battery management system, together with a focus on cyber-security.

CRF

CRF has the mission to develop and transfer innovative products, processes and methodologies in order to improve the competitiveness of the products of FCA. CRF also conducts collaborative research initiatives at the national and international levels in partnership with all the key public and private stakeholders concerned with Sustainable Mobility, targeting specifically the industrial exploitation of research.

CRF develops research and innovation along the three principal axes of sustainability: Environmental Sustainability, which encompasses all aspects relating to energy efficiency as well as to the reduction of the impact on the environment over the entire lifecycle of the vehicle; Social Sustainability, focusing on the safety of transportation systems through the development of active, passive, preventive and cooperative solutions while addressing the mobility of all users irrespective of their specific needs; Economically sustainable competitiveness, oriented towards viable innovation, i.e., improving the performance and functionality of new vehicles in a cost-effective manner.

Contribution to MARBEL

CRF will contribute to MARBEL requirements and testing, and will provide guidance on module design and manufacturing, welding, adhesive and mechanical joints. CRF will also support in Housing design, manufacturing, dismantling and recycling advisory and the selection of materials and plant technologies. Finally, CRF will run testing up to pre-normative and support in the testing and design iteration.

OTC

OTCengineering (Outsourcing Technological Company and Engineering) is a high-tech company specialized in End-to-End Connectivity and Engineering solutions for intelligent, connected and autonomous mobility. With our high technological value and innovative DNA, we have been delivering solutions since 2010. We have a team of more than 40 (direct and indirect) engineers and offices in Spain and India.

Focused on the digital revolution on mobility, we are delivering exclusive and unique solutions to our customers to burst into the digital revolution, to engage directly with the customers and generate new after-sales premium services by addressing better the end-user specific needs.

Contribution to MARBEL

OTCengineering is in charge of developing an intelligent Smart Cell Manager that will reduce the total wiring of the battery packs and improve their management during the charging and discharging process. Which will generate a direct impact on the total battery weight and cell life.

Ficosa

Ficosa is a global company dedicated to creating high-tech vision, safety, efficiency and connectivity solutions for the automotive industry. Founded in 1949 and headquartered in Barcelona, Ficosa currently employs more than 9,250 people in 17 countries in Europe, North and South America and Asia. It is a global partner of Panasonic. 8% of sales are invested in R&D.

Contribution to MARBEL

Ficosa eMobility co-leads the working packages related to Ultra-Fast Charge, EVSE communication, Power-circuit dimensioning, BMS Functional Safety and Sensor selection.

SINTEF

SINTEF is one of Europe's largest independent research organizations with 2000 employees and a turnover of 330 million € in 2018. SINTEF is an independent non-commercial organization. In 2018, SINTEF supported the development of more than 3500 companies via research and development in materials technology, applied chemistry, biotechnology, technology management and other fields.

Contract research carried out by SINTEF covers all scientific and technical areas, and ranges from basic research through applied research to commercialization of results into new products and business ideas.

SINTEF long experience in experimental characterization and numerical modelling processes and properties for metallic materials. They have substantial laboratory infrastructures for small-scale and large-scale testing and verification of materials and components.

Contribution to MARBEL

As expert in welding and integrity of metallic materials and components subjected to fatigue and corrosion, SINTEF will contribute to getting increased strength in aluminium welds and joints by developing welding procedures and joining principles with significantly improved strength with respect to current standards.

ASAS

ASAS is one of the most remarkable industrial enterprises in Turkey with its 5 state-of-the-art production facilities in Akyazi, Sakarya region and over 2000 employees and export to over 80 countries. Based on its stable financial growth trend since its establishment in 1990, ASAS was listed No 62 out of Top 500 companies in ISO 500 Turkey in 2018 which turnover is 555 mio. dollars and became one of the leading manufacturers in Europe. ASAS generates solutions and adds value to all sectors where it operates, thanks to its innovative products, technology, R&D Center which is a first and only in its sector, and its services.

Contribution to MARBEL

ASAS will contribute directly to the production of the electrical car battery housing profiles system. Firstly, extrusion die will be designed and it will be approved with QFORM extrusion simulation program. New 6xxx aluminium alloy will be developed with JMatPro metallurgical simulation program. After confirmation of alloy and extrusion die, new developed aluminium alloy billets will be produced with direct chill casting process. After that, homogenization thermal treatment operation will apply to the billets to make billets' microstructure stabilize and be ready to extrude. Characterization methods and quality control techniques will be used in order to provide desired properties by automotive industry for electrical cars.

AVL Thermal and HVAC

AVL Thermal and HVAC GmbH, headquartered in Heilbronn, is a German subsidiary of the AVL List GmbH which is the world's largest independent company for the development, simulation and testing of all types of powertrain systems.

Always at the heart of automotive engineering, with project offices and workspaces in Ingolstadt, Munich, Stuttgart and Wolfsburg, the AVL Thermal and HVAC provides industry-leading knowhow in the fields of thermal management, thermal system development, heating- and cooling cycle, air conditioning, air flow, cabin comfort, fluid management, NVH and aerodynamics for complete vehicles, all powertrains both conventional and xEV but also for non-automotive industries.

Contribution to MARBEL

AVL-THD will develop a simulation model for the thermal aspects of the battery from cell to pack level.

AVL IT

AVL is the world's largest independent company for the development, simulation and testing of all types of powertrain systems (hybrid, combustion engine, transmission, electric drive, batteries, fuel cell and control technology), their integration into the vehicle and is increasingly taking on new tasks in the field of assisted and autonomous driving as well as data intelligence. The company was founded in 1948 with the headquarters in Graz, Austria

AVL is also strongly present in Italy with an Headquarter in Turin and a Technical Center in Reggio Emilia, where a new HV Prototypes Laboratory was inaugurated in 2020.

Contribution to MARBEL

AVL IT will lead the assembly and dismantling activity on modules and battery packs. AVL IT will also support all the activities related the Battery requirements definition, the design and the test campaign.

TES-RECUPYL

TES-AMM and former RECUPYL are operating in lithium ion activities since 2006 in 2 sites (France and Singapore). French site (partner in this project) is operating since 2008 an industrial installation dedicated to power pack batteries from e-mobility and allowed by permit from environment authorities. Through the first company RECUPYL SAS, TES-RECUPYL as cumulated experience within 4 European projects as well as 5 French National projects all dedicated to recycling advanced batteries.

Beside mechanical and electrical assets, TES-REC has in France a full pilot plant for treatment of mixed cathode-anodes powder using sustainable hydrometallurgy process with free-water release. Upsizing the technology led to first industrial facility in Asia using hydrometallurgy at 6000T/y.

Contribution to MARBEL

TES-REC will be in charge of safe and smart dismantling, as well as a new approach of state of charge evaluation.

3.2.2.4 News & Events

This page will show articles on MARBEL project advances and results, as well as general assembly meetings or articles written by partners on project topics.

It will also include an agenda announcing events where MARBEL consortium is attending or participating (conferences, meetings, fairs, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

Within this page MARBEL events such as the final conference, webinars and workshops will be announced and promoted. Each event will count with a specific page with the information on the event, agenda and form to register. After the event, the presentations and documents delivered during the event will be made available for download through the page, as well as video recording of the sessions.

Figure 23: View of "News & Events" page

3.2.2.5 Results

This page will gather all public materials of the project, including visual materials, videos, public deliverables, scientific publications and media features. Specific pages for each type of content will be created depending on the number of results for a correct visualisation.

Figure 24: View of MARBEL results page - <https://marbel-project.eu/results/>

3.2.2.5.1 WP and deliverables

This page will include a short description of project WPs and a list of all deliverables to be prepared during the project and will provide access to the executive summary of confidential ones and full access to the public ones.

3.2.2.5.2 Promotional materials

Page giving access to all project promotional materials produced (rollups, posters, infosheets, etc.).

3.2.2.5.3 Scientific publications

Page giving access to all scientific publications related to the project's research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.

3.2.2.5.4 Audiovisual materials

A page to allocate all MARBEL audiovisual materials will be created.

3.2.2.5.5 Media

Section created to include the project's press releases and key media coverage on the project.

3.2.2.6 CollaBAT

This page will provide information on CollaBat and will be allocating information on joint dissemination activities with other projects. The page will be created in the next months, once CollaBAT is better defined. Some preliminary content for this page is detailed below:

MARBEL is part of CollaBat cluster (COLLABorative BATtery) which aims at virtually clustering independent R&D projects on electric battery system developments jointly addressing the technical scope areas of the LC-BAT-10 topic. Through the cluster, the main objective of CollaBat is to achieve a higher level of impact beyond project level, contributing more strongly to the adoption of the next generation of electro mobility in Europe by 2030, in alignment with the targets and timeline defined in the ERTRAC electrification roadmap.

CollaBat coordinators trust that together as a cluster they will produce a greater impact by delivering innovations that cover different demonstration vehicles, dismantling concepts and recycling strategies.

CollaBat projects

- **LIBERTY - Lightweight Battery System for Extended Range at Improved Safety**
LIBERTY's overall target is upgrading EV battery performance, safety and lifetime from a lifecycle and sustainability point of view. The key objectives of LIBERTY are to achieve a range of at least 500 km on a fully charged battery pack, halved charging times, an ultimate safe battery system, a long battery lifetime of over 300,000 km for first life, the ability to reuse the battery pack for second life applications and sustainability over the battery pack's entire life cycle.

3.2.2.7 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@marbel-project.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

Figure 25: View of contact page - <https://marbel-project.eu/contact/>

3.2.3 Layout

The MARBEL website's menu is available from all pages, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they reached the sight.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Figure 26: MARBEL website layout

Figure 27: MARBEL website footer

Figure 28: View of MARBEL header

3.2.4 Managing and updating policy

The website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The MARBEL website will be updated with new content and information every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved or there is other news worth publishing.

3.2.5 Analytics

MARBEL website has installed **Matomo** in the platform's back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services and third parties.

Figure 29: View of Matomo Analytics panel

3.2.6 Site hosting, installation and maintenance

Eurecat has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

On the other hand, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end adding content and updating it regularly. All pages have been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that MARBEL website is well positioned in the browsers.

3.2.7 Data protection

MARBEL website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR. See the legal warning, cookies policy and privacy policy on Annex.

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) on July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD “Guidelines on the Use of Cookies”, compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click “I accept”. In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website www.marbel-project.eu, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

Figure 30: View of cookies banner allowing the user to deactivate non-necessary cookies

3.3 Digital / printed materials

EUT is the partner responsible designed and produced different types of promotional materials by month 5 of the project, including a **factsheet**, a **rollup**, a **trifold**, a **poster layout** and a **general presentation** to support the partners’ dissemination activities.

All materials will follow the project’s visual identity guidelines (mentioned in section 3.1.2) and will be available to all consortium members in a digital format. The materials will be also available publicly on the project’s website.

This set of materials will be updated at different stages of the project to include up-to-date information of the advances and results (M32, M40).

Figure 31: Proposed design of MARBEL flyer (left) and rollups (right)

3.4 Audiovisual materials

Engaging audio-visual materials (e.g. videos) will be produced to present the key aspects of the project, including the

Audio-visual material produced within the project framework will be published on the MARBEL website and promoted on all project channels (social media, etc.). A number of videos are planned, including the following:

- **Videos of short interviews (M12 – M24)** - Short interviews with project partners about topics related to the project. EUT, together with FRAUNHOFER-IWU, will decide on the topics of interest for the audience of the project and will prepare the interview questions (sent in advance to partners) to produce short video interviews. The videos will be recorded during consortium meetings or recorded remotely (e.g. using Microsoft Teams), and then edited and published by EUT.
- **Project conceptual video (M36):** Video explaining the main objectives of the project, its benefits and impact for the industry, the society and the environment. It will combine partners quotes with images on the work done.

The production of other audio-visual materials will be evaluated among the consortium if any other opportunities arise. Partners will be able to propose other video topics and produce complementary videos on their contribution to MARBEL project.

3.5 Social Media

EUT is responsible for managing the MARBEL social media accounts and its content. A Twitter channel for MARBEL has already been created ([@MARBEL_H2020](#)) and is used to promote project materials and news. A YouTube channel will be created as soon as the first project video is available.

Other social media accounts, such as LinkedIn and Facebook, are not currently planned. However, the need and benefits of creating these accounts will be reviewed and revisited later on in the project and addressed in the updates of the Communication and Dissemination Plan.

All partners will contribute spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

The project coordinator will be in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels

3.5.1 Twitter

Figure 32: View of MARBEL twitter account

The MARBEL Twitter account will be managed by EUT, with the support of project partners for its correct management.

The main objective of this account is to raise awareness on the potential impacts of MARBEL novel batteries for the society, the environment and the industry, as well as to promote the solution to key stakeholders in the automotive value chain. Twitter will be also used to connect with EU institutions and related projects and initiatives.

Relevant stakeholders and partners with a professional Twitter account will be followed by the MARBEL account in order

to boost the visibility of the account.

3.5.1.1 Account management

EUT will create a regular plan of content to be disseminated through the MARBEL Twitter account. All consortium partners can propose content (text, images, videos...) to be distributed in this channel and spread the word through their own social media channels by sharing and engaging with the content.

A Hootsuite account, a tool facilitating the publication of content and activity monitoring, has been created for scheduling tweets and shortening URLs. Comments and answers will be managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

3.5.1.2 Content strategy

When creating and publishing content about the project, EUT and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations in order to maximise the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise the project's impact, and encourages market uptake to secure a critical mass of early adopters of the smart services and platform among the viticulture sector.

Content strategy:

- **Disseminating project activities:** sharing information on project events, milestones, developments accomplished, and other dissemination activities organised by the project, including text and photos if possible.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on electric vehicles, batteries, Battery Management Systems, sustainable mobility, lightweight materials for automotive, electrochemistry, etc.
- **Disseminating audio-visual and promotional materials produced** (to make the project more accessible/understandable).
- **Sharing news and articles published on the website** to increase traffic.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, the frequent use of the following hashtags is proposed:
 - **Project:** #MARBEL #MARBELproject #ResearchImpactEu #Horizon2020 #H2020
 - **EV & industry:** #ElectricVehicles #automotive #EV #sustainablelectromobility #EVcharging #electriccar #emobility #electricmobility #EVs #electricity #Hybridcar #eMobility #renewableEnergy
 - **Batteries:** #batterypack #battery #BMS #batteries #energystorage #recycling #energy #leadbatteries #aluminum #storage #charging #lithium #Batteries4EU #BatteriesRegulation #EUBatteriesAlliance #BatteriesEurope
 - **Other:** #sustainability #innovation #circulareconomy #cleanenergy #environment #climatechange #ZeroEmission #AI #lifecycle #thefutureiselectric #EUGreenDeal #decarbonisation
- Project partners (@Eurecat_news, @thi_ingolstadt, @IREC_Energia @ICCSntua @ApplusIDIADA @Fraunhofer_IWU) will be mentioned when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.
- Accounts and content from projects funded under the same topic (@GHOST_H2020, @ihcobatt, @Userchi_H2020 @erc_artistic @hydra_battery, etc.) will also be mentioned and retweeted.

Branding strategy:

- Twitter posts will be prepared covering fairs, trade shows, congresses and other events where MARBEL participates, using the official hashtag of the event (e.g., #EUGreenWeek, #TheBatteryShow, etc.).
- The official MARBEL Twitter account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project

Influencer strategy:

- Accounts such as @EU_H2020 @EuScienceInnov @CORDIS_EU @EU_commission @EUClimateAction @Energy4Europe @EV_research @EU_ERMA @Av_Batteries @RechargeEurope @EASE_ES @InnoEnergyEU will be regularly mentioned in tweets in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.

- Influencers in the field of sustainable mobility, electric vehicles, batteries, fast charging, second-use and lightweight design among other topics will be identified and mentioned in relevant posts.
- Stakeholder’s accounts will be identified to promote follow-back and to increase the number of MARBEL followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

3.5.1.3 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated in order to measure the Twitter KPIs (see Section 2.3.2 for more information) and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Figure 33: View of Twitter analytics profile

3.5.2 YouTube

The European Commission recommends the use of audio-visual resources to bring the results of the research projects closer to the general public.

Following this recommendation, a YouTube Channel will be created to allocate all videos produced during the project as soon as the first video is ready. Videos will be shared on the website and on project’s social media accounts for a broader impact.

3.5.3 Partners channels

Each partner will transmit MARBEL news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.marbel-project.eu or in the project Twitter account.

MARBEL’ partners impact on social media channels will reach more than **31K users on Twitter**, more than **299K on LinkedIn**, more than **334K on Facebook** followers and **8K in Instagram**.

Table 7: Partners Social Media channels

PARTNER	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	Instagram
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/	@Eurecat_News	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecat.org/	NA
THI	https://www.linkedin.com/sch	@th_ingolstadt	https://www.facebook.com	@thingolstadt_official

	ool/technische-hochschule- ingolstadt		om/thingolstadt	
IREC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/institut-de-reerca-en-energia-de-catalunya/	@IREC_energia	NA	NA
ICCS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/iccs-episey-ntua/	@iccsNtua	NA	NA
IDIADA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/applusi-diada/	@ApplusIDIADA	https://www.facebook.com/Aplusplusidiada	@applusidiada
AVL-IT AVL-DE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/avl/	@AVL_list	https://www.facebook.com/AVL.List	NA
CRF	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fcagroup/	NA	https://www.facebook.com/Stellantis	NA
PTS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/powertech-systems-sas/	NA	https://www.facebook.com/powertech.eu/	NA
OTC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/otcengineering/	@otcengineering	NA	NA
SINTEF	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sintef/	@SINTEF	https://www.facebook.com/sintefhq/	https://www.instagram.com/sintefhq/
FICO	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ficosa-international/	@FICOSA_Int	https://www.facebook.com/ficosaofficialpage	NA
ASAS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/asasaluminyum-sanayi-ve-ticaret-as/	@Asasaluminyum	https://www.facebook.com/asasaluminyum/?ref=ts	@asasaluminyum
AGRATI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrati-group/	NA	https://www.facebook.com/Agrati-Group-1518539201754170	NA
FW-IWU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fraunhofer-iwu/	@Fraunhofer_IWU	https://www.facebook.com/fraunhofer.iwu/	@fraunhofer.iwu

	mpany/fraunhoferiwu		om/FraunhoferIWU/	
TES-REC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/tes-it-solutions	NA	NA	NA

3.6 Media relations

Press releases will be written and sent to relevant media at regular intervals (**4 press releases written during the project**), focusing on the release of research results, milestones, meetings, attendance to or organisation of events etc., and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible (e.g. EU Green Week, European Battery Recycling Week, European Mobility Week, etc.).

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English for providing feedback (where appropriate), giving them the opportunity to adapt the documents in their corporate language and to circulate it among their regional media contacts.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented to a specific stakeholder group may be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator and Communication Leader (EUT). Also, MARBEL partners will consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to showcase the main project results to media.

In the framework of the project, a database with the contact details of partners' communication officers has been created, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase the project impact across European media outlets.

A database with specialised media covering Electric Vehicles and Batteries will be created, primarily with outlets located in the partners' countries.

During the project a **minimum of 25 publications in generalist media outlets** and **3 articles in key specialized magazines** such as the listed in table 8 are planned. The schedule, partner responsible and magazine selection, as well as the tracking of those media appearance, will be treated analogue to the journal publications.

The objective is a wider range of readers reaching the project topics involved in academia as well as industry. An initial list of European / Global specialised media outlets identified as relevant to promote MARBEL outputs include:

Table 8: List of specialized outlets

Outlet name	Website	Language
Autovolt – The Electric and Hybrid Vehicle Magazine	https://www.autovolt-magazine.com	English
Charged - Electric Vehicles Magazine	https://chargedevs.com	English
Batteries and Energy Storage Technology	https://www.bestmag.co.uk	English
Energy Storage	https://www.energy-storage.news	English
Electrek	https://electrek.co	English
Electric & Hybrid Vehicle Technology	https://www.electrichybridvehicletechnology.com	English
GreenCar Reports	https://www.greencarreports.com/news/mobility	English
eVehicle Technology	https://www.evehicletechnology.com	English

EV Tech News	https://evtechnews.in	English
Inside EVs	https://insideevs.com/news	English
Car Magazine	https://www.carmagazine.co.uk/electric/	English
Evpro Motor	https://www.evpro.es	Spanish
Ecomotion	http://www.ecomotion.es/	Spanish
Híbridos y Eléctricos	https://www.hibridosyelectricos.com	Spanish

3.6.1 Press release propose calendar

Press releases will be following WP work and main deliverables and milestones.

An initial calendar of press releases to be written is as follows:

Table 9: Preliminary press release calendar

MARBEL press release plan		Partners responsible
M1	1 st press release of the project	EUT, distributed in partners regions
M30	Battery pack and components	EUT, AVL-IT
M37	BMS operation and validated	EUT, IREC, PTS
M42	Final project results	EUT, FW-IWU

3.7 Academic dissemination

3.7.1 Scientific publications

Reports or outcomes resulting from the project activities will be published in scientific journals related to the project's fields. During the project period at **least eight publications in peer-reviewed journals are planned**. As the appearance of results and technical maturity is not yet exactly plannable the schedule of these actions is flexible being controlled by EUT and FH-IWU and follows the work package plan.

During the quarterly meetings of the WP-leaders relevant results will be discussed and partners, timing set and journals chosen. The type of journals shall be related to the matter of results such as batteries, energy storage, electrochemistry, materials.

Partners will ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications published via gold open access, whenever available (provided via the publisher when an article is published), and/or green open access via an online repository (Open Aire/ Zenodo) to ensure a long-term preservation and availability of the publication. 30% of the publications are aimed to be in collaboration of two or more project partners.

Publications will be also published in researchers' Research Gate pages (whenever applicable).

An initial list of open access journals of interest for publishing MARBEL results has been defined, as follows:

Table 10: List of identified journals

Journal name
World Electric Vehicle Journal
International Journal of Electric and Hybrid Vehicles
Journal of Power Sources
Batteries
Journal of Materials Processing Technology
Acta Physica Polonica A
Sakarya University Journal of Science
Journal of Energy Storage
Batteries and Supercaps

3.7.2 Participation to events targeting the academic community

The attendance at scientific conferences with poster presentations, exhibitions and oral presentations of the project results being held is addressed to reach the academic community. These lectures are partially peer-reviewed and reach a large audience during short term during the event itself and long term in the conference transcripts.

A wide range of conferences and academic fora are suitable for the exhibition and publication of the MARBEL results, covering, but not limited, the topics such as electric vehicles, EV batteries, battery cells, battery recyclability, electrochemistry, materials for automotive, etc.

Dissemination will mainly focus on the partners' countries (Spain, Italy, France, Denmark, Turkey, Germany, Norway and Greece). Partners will also consider attending events taking place in other European countries targeting communities strongly related to the project objectives, certainly including academia in the fields of EV batteries or the sustainable transport community.

Participation to academic events will be discussed during WP-leaders' meetings. An excel file allocated in Sharepoint folder will be available for partners to note their planned activities or the identification of any events of interest.

A non-exhaustive list of events already identified as relevant to disseminate MARBEL activities and outcomes are presented in table 11.

Table 11: Identified events targeting academia

EVENT NAME	TYPE	DATES NEXT EDITION	CITY	COUNTRY
Electric Vehicles Materials Conferences	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
Transport Research Arena (TRA)	Conference	November 2022	Lisbon	Portugal
EV batteries conference	Conference	November 2021	Online	Online
International Conference for Batteries Recycling	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
Battery Megafactories	Conference	December 2021	Berlin	Germany
Mission 1000 Batteries	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
Electric Vehicles Battery Tech	Conference	October 2021	Stuttgart	Germany
ICBTEV 2021: 15. International Conference on	Conference	November 2021	Tokyo	Japan

<u>Battery Technology and Electric Vehicles</u>				
<u>Accelerate the Next Wave of Automotive Mobility</u>	Conference	September 2021	Novi	Michigan (USA)
<u>Battery Conference</u>	Conference	April 2021	Online	Online
<u>Battery Safety Summit</u>	Conference	June 2021	Online	Online
<u>World Aluminium Conference Series</u>	Conference	June 2021	Online	Online
Metals, Minerals and Society Annual Meeting and Exhibition	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
<u>Electric Vehicles Materials Conference</u>	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD

3.7.3 Webinars

During the last year the importance and acceptance for webinars is enormously increasing. Especially in the academic community webinars are used to achieve scientifically new information and material for lecturing.

Webinar will be broadly advertised through the MARBEL website and communication channels. After the sessions, the content will be published at the MARBEL-website and YouTube. For more information, please have a look at section 3.8.2.

3.7.4 Training activities

MARBEL partners will develop training contents to provide training services during and after the project to transfer the knowledge acquired during the project to companies, research centres and European SMEs working in the project fields, as well as disseminate the project results to the scientific, education and business community and pave the path towards exploitation.

Training activities will be considered before the start of the 3rd year of the project and will be mostly carried out during the 3rd and 4th year by Universities (THI, ICCS) and research centres (EUT, FRAUNHOFER, IREC) conforming the consortium.

The training activities are aimed both at the academic/scientific community. Additionally, they include the horizontal transfer of MARBEL knowledge within the project partners.

On the scientific side training course programmes will be held for undergraduate, PhDs programmes, master, summer courses.

Training activities will be done in a series of formats, including specialised courses, open days, online tutorials and materials and the inclusion of project results into education programmes (undergraduate degrees, post-graduate courses, master's, etc).

Since now, partners have identified EUT specialised courses in EV-batteries and THI e-mobility training programme as potential for MARBEL training activities.

3.8 Dissemination to the industry

3.8.1 Participation to Exhibitions and conferences

Project partners will also connect with the electric vehicles sector (OEMs, Tier 1, Tier 2 companies) in national and international congresses, exhibitions and fairs to disseminate the benefits and potential of MARBEL battery solution and facilitate the uptake of novel batteries into the market.

There is **an attendance of more than 20 conferences, international fairs and key market events planned**. Aside from lectures being held, the objective is the exhibition of MARBEL-outputs or distribution of promotion material. No matter if digital or face-to-face events, the activities initiate first customer contacts and enlarge the awareness of the project, consortium and activities.

The following list of events will be continuously supplemented and includes experiences of the partners and their already established network activities:

Table 12: List of industrial exhibitions and conferences

EVENT NAME	TYPE	DATES NEXT EDITION	CITY	COUNTRY
AABC Europe: advanced automotive battery conference	Conference	January 2022	TBD	TBD
EARPA Form Forum	Workshop	November 2021	Brussels	Belgium
International Aluminium	Congress	TBD	Virtual	Virtual
Automobile Barcelona	Exhibition	July 2021	Barcelona	Spain
Battery Electric Vehicle Architectures Congress	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
Electric & Hybrid Vehicle Technology Expo Europe	Exhibition	May 2021	Online	Online
European Electric Vehicle Batteries Summit	Conference	June 2021	Rotterdam	The Netherlands
Power2Drive	Exhibition	July 2021	Munich	Germany
The Battery Show	Exhibition & conference	May 2021	Virtual	Virtual

3.8.2 Industrial events

Workshops are planned in the **second half of the project period** as project results will be the basement of these events. These workshops are primarily addressed to a certain group of participants but will be open for other invited companies as partners suggest their participation to spread and discuss results, further actions and potentially adapt the development action to the requirements of the industrial sector. That way the workshops are an important tool to verify the compliance to the needs of the applicants.

Addressed stakeholders of the workshops are:

- **Automotive / battery sector** (OEMs and Tier1/2 suppliers e.g. Turkey Automotive Sub-Contractors Society (ASAS) and associations such as EARPA, VDA, etc.)
- **Linked industrial sectors** such as the Turkey Aluminium Surface Treatment Society (ASAS)
- **Advisory board**

Webinars will be announced through the project communication channels (website and social media), and through the MARBEL mailing list. The sessions will be recorded, and recordings will be uploaded to the project's YouTube channel.

Details on the proposed general topic of the workshops and tentative dates are listed below:

Proposed topic	Leading partner	Place	Approximate date
Workshop #1: Advanced recycled aluminium alloys for EV applications	ASAS, EUT	Turkey	M20
Workshop #2: Advanced novel modular battery pack system	EUT, IREC	Barcelona	M37
Workshop #3: Test procedures and eVIL	THI, IDIADA	Germany	M41

On the other hand, **webinars** will be held by one or more partners with a duration of 30-40 minutes talk followed by 20-30 minutes discussion and answering of questions. As the intention is a combination of workshop, training and general information the advantage is the independence from schedule and location as these events will be recorded and uploaded to the MARBEL-website and YouTube. In that way the environmental impact is limited as the objective is a minimum of 25 attendees at the event itself followed by additional audience of the available online information with a wider distribution rate.

Details on the proposed general topic of the webinars and tentative dates are listed below:

Proposed topic	Leading partner	Approximate date
Webinar #1: Lightweight materials for EV vehicles	EUT, SINTEF	M25
Webinar #2: BMS Management	IREC	M36
Webinar #3: Battery cooling and metal foam	FW-IWU	M39
Webinar #4: Design for assembly / disassembly and 2 nd Life	EUT, AVL, THI	M40

3.8.3 One-to-one meetings

The direct dissemination by one-to-one meetings is a key issue of the dissemination strategy as the personal network of the partners is far more effective compared with a top-down strategy by project management.

During the project period at least 30 meetings with **automotive/battery companies**, including OEMs, Tier1/2 and SMEs are planned to gather their needs and guide them through the innovative MARBEL battery pack solution to ease exploitation (e.g. VW, AUDI, BAE Batteries GmbH, etc.). The meetings are aimed at the technology transfer and the improvement of the process creating the basement for a later serial production.

In addition to these sector specific actions, there will be at least 20 meetings for direct dissemination with **linked industrial sectors** planned. These activities will be supported by the workshops mentioned in capture 3.8.2.

3.9 Dissemination to the society

Participation to events or initiatives for the general public to generate awareness on electric vehicles and batteries:

- **European Mobility week** - <https://mobilityweek.eu/home/> (*each September*) EUROPEANMOBILITYWEEK is the European Commission's flagship awareness-raising campaign on sustainable urban mobility. It promotes behavioural change in favour of active mobility, public transport, and other clean, intelligent transport solutions.
- **European Battery Recycling Week** - <https://www.weeeireland.ie/2020/09/07/european-battery-recycling-week-7-13-september-2020/> (*each September powered by EUCOBAT*) Week long initiative powered by EUCOBAT, the Pan-European association of national battery collection organisations of which WEEE Ireland is a member, will see local awareness campaigns take place in member countries throughout the week, reminding the public of the importance of collecting, sorting and recycling their used batteries.
- **European Sustainable Energy Week** - https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/eu-sustainable-energy-week/eu-sustainable-energy-week-eusew-2021-oct-25_en (*each October*) The event comprises a 3-day digital policy conference, the EUSEW Awards, the second European Youth Energy Day as well as 1:1 video meetings, virtual stands and other networking activities. Participants will also have access to online side events and Energy Days, digital events taking place all over Europe.
- **Global Recycling Day** - <https://www.globalrecyclingday.com> (*each 18th of March*)
- **Pint of Science** - <https://pintofscience.com> (*each May*) The Pint of Science festival aims to deliver interesting and relevant talks on the latest science research in an accessible format to the public – mainly across bars, pubs, cafes and other public spaces. We want to provide a platform which allows people to discuss research with the people who carry it out and no prior knowledge of the subject is required.

3.10 Clustering activities

During the MARBEL project execution, project partners will be in contact with the coordinators of other related projects, relevant industry associations and companies, and European institutions related to the project's fields.

Synergies between MARBEL and other groups will be established through attending relevant events or working groups that are organised or attended by the institutions listed in the sections below. Additionally, partners will actively interact with the initiatives promoted by these groups and contribute with content on the project to feed associations' newsletters and publications, when possible.

3.10.1 Joint actions with sister projects

Connections with other projects, initiatives and knowledge hubs with complementary interests will be sought at national, EU and international level with the aim of enhancing synergies while avoiding duplication of efforts in the dissemination of results.

Partnering with other projects and initiatives will allow to join efforts and also have a stronger voice when communicating with target audiences. Some of the MARBEL sister projects and

initiatives identified to date, related to the EV batteries, battery recyclability, materials for automotive, etc., are listed in Table 13.

Table 13: MARBEL sister projects

Initiative	Short description
LIBERTY (ending June 2024)	LIBERTY's overall target is upgrading EV battery performance, safety and lifetime from a lifecycle and sustainability point of view.
HELIOS (ending Dec 2024)	Development and integration of innovative materials, designs, technologies and processes to create a new concept of smart, modular and scalable battery pack for a wide range of electric vehicles used in urban electromobility services, with improved performance, energy density, safety, lifetime and LCoS (Levelized Cost of Storage).
ALBATROSS (ending Dec 2024)	Addresses the needs of European Electric and Hybrid-Electric passenger vehicle market by overcoming driver concerns relating to battery range and anxiety, cost, long-term reliability and excessive charging times.
GHOST (ending Dec 2021)	Designing both a novel and modular battery system and prototyping, manufacturing and dismantling techniques for next generation of lithium-ion battery systems.
SELFIE (ending May 2022)	Innovative solutions of Battery Thermal Management System (BTMS) that will allow fast battery charging.
i-HECobatt (ending Jun 2022)	Smart, cost bursting industrial battery heat exchanger to minimize the impact on full electric vehicle range in extreme conditions.
FITGEN (ending December 2021)	Functionally integrated e-axle ready for implementation in third generation electric vehicles.
CEVOLVER (ending April 2022)	Optimising the development and operation of electric vehicles using cutting edge technologies, components and systems. Ensure a leap forward in user's confidence, functionalities and energy efficiency of future EVs.
INCIT-EV (ending Decr 2023)	Demonstration of an innovative set of charging infrastructures, technologies and its associated business models, ready to improve the EV users experience beyond early adopters, thus, fostering the EV market share in the EU.
USER-CHI (ending Jan 2024)	Integration of innovative charging technologies and put the user at the centre of the entire transition. The project will integrate the technological tools, business models and regulatory measures to be tested and validated in five EU cities.
VISION-xEV (ending December 2021)	Methodologies for faster industrialization of xEV considering simulation tools and new methods for components. Vehicle integration of powertrain components.
CarE-Service (ending May 2021)	Circular Economy Business Models for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services.

3.10.1.1 CollaBAT

The **CollaBAT cluster** (Collaborative Battery) aims at **virtually clustering** independent R&D projects on EV battery system developments jointly addressing the scope of the LC-BAT-10-2020 topic.

Dissemination is something that will mutually benefit all partners in creating awareness about the project activities in the field of sustainable energy transition, their progress, potential and environmental benefits.

The separate project internet pages will be accessible through the umbrella website www.collabat.eu, being a joint landing page. This way, the dissemination activities in the

construction of the website can be combined, money can be saved, and the website can be build more professionally, increasing the reach and impact for all.

Detailed joint dissemination actions include:

- **Events:** organization of a mid-term and final event with projects in the cluster opened to all stakeholder groups and media outlets of interest. Participation to other BAT-10 project events and invitation of CollaBAT project in MARBEL events.
- **Publications:** maximise dissemination via publications, both combining efforts for joint publications in external sources (journals, magazines) as well as creating dedicated unique material at CollaBAT level (e.g. common book for electromobility roadmap, joint policy recommendations on electromobility towards the EC).
- **Social Media:** joint dissemination in social media, shared news on CollaBAT projects.

3.10.2 Joint actions with EV user associations

In relation to direct dissemination and discussion with expert consumer representatives there are at least **five meetings with EV user associations** planned.

EV user associations identified to stablish synergies with include:

Name	Webste
AUVE – Association Spanish EV users	https://www.auve.org
AVERE – The Association for electromobility	https://www.avere.org
Norsk elbilforening – Association of Norweigen EV owners / users	https://elbil.no/english/about-norwegian-ev-association/
FAUVE - FEDERATION FRANCAISE des Associations d'Utilisateurs de Véhicules Electriques	https://www.ffauve.org
AVERE Turkey delegation	https://en.avere.org.tr

3.10.3 Joint actions with EU clusters, associations and initiatives

Cooperation and synergies will be established with relevant initiatives and platforms, some of which are listed below:

Name	Description	Webste
ELCA- European Lightweight Alliance	The overall objective of the European Lighting Cluster Alliance, ELCA, is to gather forces on a European level in order to increase the competitiveness of the European lighting industries.	http://elcacluster.eu
ACEA – the European Automobile Manufacturers Association	The European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA) represents the 15 major Europe-based car, van, truck and bus makers.	https://www.acea.be

EARPA Association of Automotive	– of EARPA is the association of automotive R&D organisations. It brings together the most prominent independent R&D providers in the automotive sector throughout Europe. EUT, THI, IDIADA are members.	https://www.earpa.eu/earpa/home
EUROBAT Association of European Automotive and Industrial Battery Manufacturers	- of EUROBAT objective is to study all matters of interest to storage battery manufacturers and their sub-contractors in Europe, the Middle East and Africa. EUROBAT's activities include promoting the regulatory, commercial and economic interests of the European automotive, industrial and special battery industries; facilitating the continued growth of the European industry; working with stakeholders to help develop new battery solutions.	https://www.eurobat.org
EBRA – European Battery Recycling Association	EBRA aims to develop the highest standards of professionalism in the battery recycling industry by promoting best practice in health, safety and environment and by preserving natural resources while respecting the European regulatory framework.	https://www.ebra-recycling.org
EUCOBAT European association of national collection schemes for batteries	– of Eucobat is the European association of national collection schemes for batteries. They assure that all waste batteries are collected and recycled in an ecological sound way, and contribute this way to a better environment.	https://www.eucobat.eu
EASE – European Association for Storage of Energy	The European Association for Storage of Energy (EASE) located in Brussels, Belgium, is the leading member-supported association representing organisations active across the entire energy storage value chain. EASE supports the deployment of energy storage to support the cost-effective transition to a resilient, climate-neutral, and secure energy system.	https://ease-storage.eu
ERMA – European Raw Materials Alliance	The European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA) aims to make Europe economically more resilient by diversifying its supply chains, creating jobs, attracting investments to the raw materials value chain, fostering innovation,	https://erma.eu

	training young talents and contributing to the best enabling framework for raw materials and the Circular Economy worldwide.	
Eurelectric	Eurelectric is the federation for the European electricity industry. We represent the power sector in over 32 European countries, speaking for more than 3,500 companies in power generation, distribution and supply.	https://www.eurelectric.org
CIAC Cluster	The Automotive Industry Cluster of Catalonia (CIAC) is a non-profit association open to companies operating in the automotive industry, that are based in Catalonia, and pursue R&D+i activities.	https://www.ciac.cat
EBA – European Battery Alliance	The European Battery Alliance (EBA) ensures that all Europeans benefit from safer traffic, cleaner vehicles and more sustainable technological solutions. All this will be achieved by creating a competitive and sustainable battery cell manufacturing value chain in Europe. EUT, AVL are part of EBA.	https://www.eba250.com
CLEPA - European Association of Automotive Suppliers	CLEPA is the voice of European automotive suppliers, representing over 3.000 companies which employ 5.000.000 employees. AGRATI is member pf CLEPA.	https://clepa.eu
EERA - European Energy Research Alliance	EERA is an association of European public research centres and universities with the mission to catalyse European energy research for a climate-neutral society. IREC is part of this association.	https://www.eera-set.eu
EMIRI - The Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative.	EMIRI is driving forward research and innovation in the advanced materials for low-carbon energy applications. Innovative energy technologies are required to cost-effectively meet Europe's energy and climate change challenges. IREC is member.	https://emiri.eu
Batteries 2030+	BATTERY 2030+ is the large-scale and long-term European research initiative with the vision of inventing the sustainable batteries of the future.	https://battery2030.eu/
VDA)	German Association of the Automotive Industry. FR-IWU is a member.	https://www.vda.de/en

3.11 Activities calendar

ACTIVITIES	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14
	Mar-21	Apr-21	May-21	Jun-21	Jul-21	Aug-21	Sep-21	Oct-21	Nov-21	Dec-21	Jan-22	Feb-22
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D9.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan	X											
Promotional materials first design ready			X									
Video interviews to partners										X	X	X
	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26
	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Video Interviews to partners	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Creation YouTube account	X											
Workshop 1						X						
D9.2 1 st Dissemination and exploitation report										X		
Training activities										X	X	X
Webinar 1											X	
	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38
	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Social media update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Training activities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press release: battery pack and components				X								
Promotional materials update						X						
Project conceptual video										X		
Webinar 2										X		
Press release: BMS Operated and Validated											X	
Workshop 2											X	
	M39	M40	M41	M42								
	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24								
Website update	X	X	X	X								
Social media update	X	X	X	X								
Training activities	X	X	X	X								
Webinar 3	X											
Promotional materials update		X										
Webinar 4		X										
Workshop 3			X									
D9.3 Final dissemination and exploitation report				X								
Press release: project results				X								

4. Annex

4.0 Website privacy policy

WHO IS THE DATA CONTROLLER FOR YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

Data controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“EURECAT”)

Tax ID number: G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection delegate contact: dpo@eurecat.org

FOR WHAT PURPOSE WILL BE PROCESSED YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

Your personal data received through the contact form will be processed for the purpose of managing your query or request. However, the data collected as the result of the cookies installation, will be used for collecting statistical information on the browsing of users and improve the website based on their browsing habits. You may consult further information about the cookies purposes and its data treatment at the Cookies Policy

On our website, there may be several forms that collect your personal data for specific purposes. In those cases, you will be previously informed about the specific data treatment information to each case, and your specific consent shall be sought.

IS IT MANDATORY TO PROVIDE ALL THE INFORMATION REQUESTED IN THE FORMS ON THE WEBSITE?

The user must complete the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal information or to partially do so may mean that Fundació Eurecat cannot meet your requests and, consequently, Fundació Eurecat will be exempt from any liability for the non-provision or incomplete provision of the requested services.

The personal data provided by the User to Fundació Eurecat must be up to date so that the information in our records is current and without errors. The user will be liable for the veracity of the data provided.

HOW LONG WILL YOUR PERSONAL DATA BE RETAINED FOR?

The personal data obtained, will be kept for the duration of the purposes for which it was collected for and its erasure is not requested, and consent is not revoked. The personal data, also, will be kept, in any case, during the legal term applicable.

WHAT IS THE LAWFUL BASIS FOR US TO PROCESS YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

The lawful basis for the processing of your data is the consent provided through acceptance of the data processing clause.

WHAT RECIPIENTS WILL YOUR DATA BE SHARED WITH?

The Personal data received through the forms of the website may be shared with members of the project for the exclusive purpose of managing your query or request and be able to send you the

latest news about the project through periodic newsletters. You may consult the list of members here.

The personal data may be shared to third-parties whose develop services to the Data Controller, those ones who has access to the personal data will not treat the personal data fort their own or different purposes and they will not sold or rent them.

The personal data will not be passed on to any other third-parties, unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

WHAT ARE THE RIGHTS REGARDING YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

The user may exercise their right to access their personal data, to request the rectification of inaccurate data and, where applicable, to request the data to be erased if it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. The user may also exercise their right to data portability and to the restriction of or opposition to the processing of their data, in certain circumstances and for reasons related to their specific situation.

The user also has the right to revoke their consent at any time, without any retroactive effect on the processing of their personal data carried out until that point.

The user may exercise the aforementioned rights, under the terms provided for in current legislation, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or request to do so by sending an email to legal@eurecat.org.

Should the user not receive a satisfactory response, and should they wish to make a complaint or obtain more information on any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6, Madrid).

AUTOMATED DECISIONS

The personal data shall not be submitted to automated decisions.

The personal data may be processed to create profiles according to the cookies that has been consented to installed by the user.

INTERNATIONAL DATA TRANSFERS

The personal data shall not be summited to international transfers out of the European Union. However, the Data Controller may have several suppliers that develop services out of the UE, in those cases, Fundació Eurecat shall assure that the personal data shall be treat with the legal requirements through agreement that may include standard contractual clauses or privacy certification.

WHAT SECURITY MEASURES HAS THE INSTITUTION IMPLEMENTED?

Fundació Eurecat declares that it has implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures that guarantee the security of the User's personal data and avoid its alteration, loss, processing and/or unauthorised access considering the state of technology, the nature of the stored data and the risks to which it is exposed, whether from human action or from the physical or natural environment, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.

SOCIAL MEDIA

MARBEL, a project coordinated by Fundació Eurecat has a profile on Twitter for publishing and disseminating information about the services provided through the website, interacting with users and acting as a customer service and social interaction channel.

The following are links to the privacy policies of the social networks on which MARBEL has an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/howyoutubeworks/policies/community-guidelines/>

4.1 Website legal warning

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website www.marbel-project.eu FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

ACCESS TO THE WEBSITE

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The User must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

USE OF THE WEBSITE

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

OPERATION OF THE WEBSITE

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

LIABILITY

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by accessing and/or using the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

POLICY ON LINKS

A) Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

B) Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

INTELLECTUAL AND INDUSTRIAL PROPERTY RIGHTS OF THE CONTENT

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs (source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names ("distinctive signs") are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

APPLICABLE LEGISLATION

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation.

Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

CONTACT

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

4.2 Website cookies policy

WHAT ARE COOKIES AND WHY DO WE USE THEM ON THE WEBSITE?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. The cookies that exist on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES EXIST?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies. Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.
- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES DOES THE WEBSITE USE?

Necessary cookies

- **Name:** cookielawinfo-checkbox-analytics
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Analytics".
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

- **Name:** cookielawinfo-checkbox-functional
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Functional".
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

- **Name:** cookielawinfo-checkbox-others
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Other"
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

- **Name:** cookielawinfo-checkbox-advertisement
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Advertising"
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

- **Name:** cookielawinfo-checkbox-necessary
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Necessary"
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

- **Name:** cookielawinfo-checkbox-performance
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Performance"
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

- **Name:** viewed_cookie_policy
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.
- **Expiry period:** 11 months

Performance cookies

- **Name:** __cfduid
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** The cookie is used by cdn services like CloudFare to identify individual clients behind a shared IP address and apply security settings on a per-client basis. It does not correspond to any user ID in the web application and does not store any personally identifiable information.
- **Expiry period:** 1 month.

- **Name:** ls_smartpush
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** This cookie is set by the provider Litespeed Server. This cookie allows the server to store the settings and to improve performance of the site.
- **Expiry period:** 2 months

- **Name:** YSC
- **Provider:** YouTube
- **Purpose:** This cookies are set by YouTube and is used to track the views of embedded videos.
- **Expiry period:** session

Statistics cookies

- **Name:** _pk_ses.14.3481
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** Short lived cookies used to temporarily store data for the visit.
- **Expiry period:** 30 minutes

- **Name:** _pk_id.14.3481
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** used to store a few details about the user such as the unique visitor ID.
- **Expiry period:** 1 year and 27 days

- **Name:** CONSENT
- **Provider:** marbel-project.eu
- **Purpose:** As long as this cookie exists, Matomo will know that consent has been given and automatically process the data.
- **Expiry period:** 16 years 9 months 7 days 12 hours 10 minutes

- **Name:** VISITOR_INFO1_LIVE
- **Provider:** YouTube
- **Purpose:** This cookie is set by YouTube. Used to track the information of the embedded YouTube videos on a website.

HOW DO YOU DISABLE COOKIES IN A BROWSER?

The user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending of the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered ad a Third-party cookies. For example, if the user chooses Google’s browser and use its option of translate full website, Google install cookies in

the user's computers that are not managed by the website publisher. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- Information about cookies for [Mozilla Firefox](#).
- Information about cookies for [Internet Explorer](#)
- Information about cookies for [Opera](#).
- Information about cookies for [Google Chrome](#).
- Information about cookies for [Safari](#).